

Diurnal Butterfly Species Visiting *Chamaecytisus heuffelii* (Wierzb.) Rothm. Flowers in SW Hungary

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Abstract. This study investigated one of the rarest plants in Hungary, *Chamaecytisus heuffelii* (Wierzb.) Rothm. [Fabaceae] in terms of the butterfly species that visit flowers as a nectar source. It also provides a general overview of the plant, its habitat, and geographical distribution. *Chamaecytisus heuffelii* is a highly endangered species in Hungary that may soon become extinct here. The flower-visiting butterfly species showed gradual regression. These numbers are decreasing annually. This was not caused only by habitat degradation; the main cause is probably that the area has been sprayed with chemicals for many years to control mosquitoes. The spraying was stopped a few years ago.

Keywords. Hungary, butterflies, flower visits, *Chamaecytisus heuffelii*, conservation, biodiversity

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Introduction

Chamaecytisus heuffelii is a perennial semi-shrub with a distribution confined to the Balkan region. In Hungary it is found only in the city of Pécs, where it is located within a protected rocky site. This site is likely to be the northernmost and westernmost location where the species is known to occur. As such, *Chamaecytisus heuffelii* is a distinctive component of Hungarian flora, and its conservation in its native habitat is of considerable importance for nature conservation, both in Hungary and internationally.

The expansion of Pécs, involving construction, tourism growth, and grassland degradation, presents the primary threat to its habitat. This plant, safeguarded by the Hungarian Nature Conservation Act of 2005, is reported to be under threat of extinction, as indicated by the Hungarian Red List (Király 2007).

The Havi Hill in Pécs, Hungary, is the sole location where the following formations can be found: coarse limestone and lime sandstone. This type of rock is representative of the Sarmatian floor of the Miocene. The remains of calcareous marine organisms that perished and were deposited in the shallow Sarmatian Sea, which bordered the coast 12–14 million years ago, resulted in the formation of this rock (Kraft 2000, Lehmann 2009). The height of the hill was 170–246 metres above the sea level. The hill and its surroundings have been affected by quarrying for generations, although mining operations on Havi Hill ceased in the 1950s.

The city of Pécs designated this area as a nature reserve of local importance. However, this area has been managed negligently for some years. In some cases, people have cut the entire grassland with a lawnmower, oblivious to the value of the protected plants. Not only the vegetation but also the ground fauna suffered considerable damage. To date, city authorities have not named or held accountable those responsible for this damage.

This plant's habitat is expected to have been checked continuously between 2005 and 2024. I am mainly interested in the species of butterflies that visit during the flowering period. First, I will briefly describe the habitat and geographical distribution of *Chamaecytisus heuffelii*, followed by an overview of the flower-visiting butterfly species.

Fig. 1. The Havi Hill in Pécs, Hungary: study area (white circle). Here is the only Hungarian population of the *Chamaecytisus heuffelii* (253 m | 46°05'07''N; 18°14'16''E)

Fig. 2. The city of Pécs designated this area as a nature reserve of local importance. However, this area has been managed negligently for some years. In some cases, people have cut the entire grassland with a lawnmower, oblivious to the value of the protected plants. Not only the vegetation but also the ground fauna suffered considerable damage. The *Chamaecytisus heuffelii* plant has been eradicated (bottom right).

Results

Chamaecytisus heuffelii (Wierzb.) Rothm.

Syn.: *Cytisus heuffelii* Wierzb. in Griseb. et Schenk 1852, *Cytisus austriacus* var. *heuffelii* Rchb. f. 1869, *Cytisus supinus* subsp. *austriacus* var. *heuffelii* (Wierzb.) Briq. 1894, *Cytisus austriacus* L. var. *heuffelii* (Wierzb.) C. K. Schneid 1907, *Cytisus austriacus* subsp. *heuffelii* (Wierzb.) Aschers, et Graebn, 1910, *Cytisus austriacus* var. *heuffelii* (Wierzb.) Stoj. 1925.

References. Borbás 1886; Cristofolini 1991; Gergely et al. 2017; Horvát 1945; Heywood & Frodin 1968; Kevey 1999; Király 2007; Micewski 2001; Pifkó 2005, 2010; Wirth et al. 2010

Habitat. Occurs on sand in Deliblát (in Serbia) and prefers more exposed surfaces (cf. Borbás 1886). Found in open limestone grasslands in the Iron Gate Gorge (both on the Romanian and Serbian sides) and on Havi Hill in Pécs, where the Rock Worm (*Artemisia alba* Turra) is a characteristic plant as in the adjacent, more closed grasslands.

Distribution. Albania, Austria (Cristofolini 1991), Romania, Serbia, Bulgaria, Hungary (only in Pécs; Mecsek Mountains; Király, 2009), Macedonia (Micevski, 2001), and Greece (Heywood & Frodin, 1968). In Austria, Cristofolini (1991) was the first to report the species; it was not known earlier, and the more recent Austrian descriptor (Fischer et al. 2005) does not include the species, so its presence should be investigated. Data from Albania, Bulgaria, Greece, and Macedonia are also uncertain and require confirmation.

Butterfly species observed feeding at *Chamaecytisus heuffelii* flowers

Hesperiidae (4 sp)

Hesperia comma (Linnaeus, 1758)
Ochlodes sylvanus (Esper, 1777)
Pyrgus malvae (Linnaeus, 1758)
Thymelicus lineola (Ochsenheimer, 1808)

Pieridae (3 sp)

Leptidea sinapis (Linnaeus, 1758)
Pieris rapae (Linnaeus, 1858)
P. napi (Linnaeus, 1858)

Lycaenidae (9 sp)

Celastrina argiolus (Linnaeus, 1758)
Cupido argiades (Pallas, 1771)
Cupido minimus (Fuessly, 1775)
Glaucopsyche alexis (Poda, 1761)
Hamearis lucina (Linnaeus, 1758)
Iolana iolas (Ochsenheimer, 1816)
Lycaena thersamon (Esper, 1784)
Plebeius argus (Linnaeus, 1758)
Polyommatus icarus (Rottemburg, 1775)

Nymphalidae (5 sp)

Coenonympha arcania (Linnaeus, 1761)
C. pamphilus (Linnaeus, 1758)
Melitaea trivia (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)

Vanessa atalanta (Linnaeus,1758)

V. cardui (Linnaeus,1758)

In total, 21 species were observed during the flower visits. Most Lycaenidae species prefer their flowers. Among these, *Iolana iolas* stands out. This ponto-Mediterranean species reaches the northern limit of its geographical range in Hungary (Gergely et al. 2017). It is highly protected in Hungary, with an estimated HUF of 250,000. They prefer rocky and karstic shrub forest habitats. It is extremely local and rare in Hungary. It has been extirpated from many former habitats. Stable populations were found in the Mecsek and Villány Mountains. The larval only food source is *Colutea arborescens*. The survival of the nutrient

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Figs 3–5. (3) *Chamaecytisus heuffelii* in full flower; (4) the *Iolana iolas* adult during a flower visit; (5) the geographical distribution of the *Iolana iolas* in Hungary. The species has a number of old site records, but these populations have not been confirmed by more recent research. The most stable populations are found in southern Hungary in the Mecsek and Villány Mountains (see black circles).

plant is threatened by the introduction of pine (*Pinus nigra*, *P. sylvestris*) and acacia trees (*Robinia pseudocacia*).

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Összefoglalás (Hungarian summary).

Milyen nappali lepkefajok látogatják a *Chamaecytisus heuffelii* (Wierzb.) virágait a Pécsi Havi-hegyen

Fazekas Imre

A pécsi helyi védelem alatt álló Havi-hegyen, 2009-es botanikai felmérések során összesen 287 taxon jelenlétét sikerült kimutatni (Wirth et al. 2010). Elmondható, hogy a Havi-hegy a szerzők által alkalmazott finom léptékű felmérés alapján Magyarország egyik legdiverzebb területének számít. A szerzők a 10,4 hektáros területet Pécs belvárosán belül egy diverzitási „forráspontnak” tekintik. A vizsgálatok alkalmával számos olyan növény is előkerült a területről, amelyek a Mecsekben unikálisak, vagy ritkák (pl. *Aster amellus*, *Chamaecytisus heuffelii*, *Cotoneaster integerrimus*, *Medicago monspeliaca*). Összesen 27 törvényes oltalom alatt álló faj előfordulása bizonyított. A Havi-hegy legjelentősebb botanikai értéke a Magyarországon unikális, dácikus *Chamaecytisus heuffelii*. A terület lepkefaunáját korábban senki nem kutatta. A tanulmányban a szerző a *Chamaecytisus heuffelii* virágokat látogató 21 nappali lepkéket vizsgálta 2005 és 2024 között (lásd a listát). Ezek közül kiemelkedik *Iolana iolas*. Ez a pontomediterrán faj Magyarországon éri el földrajzi elterjedési területének északi határát (Gergely et al 2017). Magyarországon fokozottan védett, eszmei értéke 250 000 forint. Előnyben részesíti sziklás és karsztos erdei élőhelyeket. Magyarországon rendkívül lokális és ritka. Számos korábbi élőhelyről eltűnt. Baranyában stabil populációkat találunk a Mecsekben és a Villányi-hegységben. Az egyetlen tápnövénye a *Colutea arborescens*. A helyi populációk fennmaradását veszélyezteti az akácerdők és feketefenyvesek terjedése és a fokozatos beerdősülés.

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